

Natural heritage digitalization and preservation supported by digital fabrication technologies

Apoyo a la digitalización y conservación del patrimonio Natural mediante tecnologías de fabricación digital

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Abstract

This study aimed to implement 3D image acquisition and postprocessing tools for natural heritage preservation of a collection of craniums from a zoology museum and a wildlife rescue center. Some of the samples were prepared by osteological preservation protocols developed in the rescue center and then digitized in a darkroom using a 3D Scanner of metrology grade, the meshes were optimized for both fabrication and visualization purposes, then some of the models were printed at the university maker space using three different technologies to be measure and analyzed with the metrology capabilities of inspection software to determine which of them provides the most accurate replicas. The obtained results demonstrate that the three technologies provide high-quality replicas, however those based on optical processes (SLA and Material jetting) generate the more accurate physical models which are of particular interest for training and learning experiences in veterinarian med, the models were successfully adapted to be uploaded to a 3D viewer platform compatible with low-cost virtual reality solutions to implemented it on environmental education activities. The experience demonstrates that photogrammetry and 3D scanning are feasible solutions to keep scientific and knowledge preservation of high-value samples composed of biological materials exposed to degradation by environmental conditions, providing new digital assets to foster outreach and educational activities for both university and rescue center interest.

Keywords: Photogrammetry, 3D modeling, Natural Heritage, 3D scanning, Osteological preservation.

Resumen

Este estudio tuvo como objetivo implementar herramientas de posprocesamiento y adquisición de imágenes 3D para la preservación de una colección de craneos de un museo de zoología y un centro de rescate de vida silvestre. Algunas de las muestras fueron preparadas mediante protocolos de preservación osteológica desarrollados en el centro de rescate y luego digitalizadas en un cuarto oscuro utilizando un escáner 3D de grado metrológico, las mallas se optimizaron tanto para fines de fabricación como de visualización, luego algunos de los modelos se imprimieron en el Espacio Maker de la universidad utilizando tres tecnologías de impresión distintas para ser medidos y analizados con las capacidades del software de inspección y así determinar cuál de ellas proporciona las réplicas más precisas. Los resultados obtenidos demuestran que las tres tecnologías proporcionan réplicas de alta calidad, pero aquellas basadas en procesos ópticos (SLA e inyección de material) generan modelos físicos más precisos que son de particular interés para experiencias

de entrenamiento y aprendizaje en medicina veterinaria, los modelos fueron cargados en una plataforma de visualización 3D compatible con soluciones de realidad virtual de bajo costo para implementarlo en actividades de educación ambiental. La experiencia demuestra que la fotogrametría y el escaneo 3D son soluciones factibles para la preservación de muestras de interés científico e histórico de alto valor compuestas de materiales biológicos susceptibles a las condiciones ambientales, proporcionando nuevos activos digitales que permitan fomentar actividades de divulgación y educación de interés tanto para universidades como para centros de rescate y museos.

Keywords: Fotogrametría, Modelado 3D, Patrimonio Natural, Escaneo 3D, Preservación osteológica.

Introduction

Natural history collections represent invaluable heritage assets for museums and Higher education research and teaching programs. In prominent museums, such material is protected to study and preserve knowledge about specimens to manage discoveries under a safeguard process. On the other hand, maintained natural heritage is of particular interest in academic contexts because it provides the chance to use them as a didactic resource to support theoretical courses and hands-on experiences with different specimens without extracting them from their natural habitats. (Martini et al., 2022).

The 3D model's collections of skeletons have demonstrated powerful tools in Higher education scenarios, the access to realistic visualization of animals and fossils, and digitization have a powerful impact on viewers as they are not commonly seen in everyday life. This can be a helpful tool to generate awareness about species' anatomy. Additionally, studying animal skeletons provides valuable information and aid in the education of future natural sciences professionals. For example, studying the anatomy of animal skeletons can help clinical disciplines better understand the species they treat and thus protect endangered species (Ye et al, 2023)

When natural science students review anatomy topics, studying skeletons can enhance their learning experience. Many students learn about wildlife through books, and since the images presented in the books are two-dimensional, students are unable to touch or see a 3D image of the structures they intend to learn about, therefore allowing these students access to natural collections that include bones can broaden the understanding of the anatomy of species (Cunningham, 2021)

Conservators use different techniques to preserve these objects over time, some of the most common materials reported during the preservation, are natural resins such as paraffin wax, PVA emulsions, or PEG as consolidated waterlogged. Nonetheless, it is always possible that these invasive conservation processes can affect the result causing a modification or damage to the specimen material because of the chemical features of those products (Guareschi, Magni & Berry, 2023).

Environmental conditions also represent a factor capable of accelerating the degradation by bioerosion processes related to the exposition of light, oxygen, and chemical reactions related to bone degradation (Caruso et al., 2018). The nonregulation of these three conditions promotes adverse conditions such as the proliferation of bacteria communities and the growth of bacteria in bone. Besides, those collections are touched and manipulated for education aims, and that can speed up more bacteria growth and damage (Eriksen et al., 2020).

Nowadays, with digital fabrication techniques becoming even more accessible, there is an opportunity to preserve those assets through new methods, one example is 3D scanning where the

digitalization based on photogrammetry technologies of natural heritage has been implemented as a preservation alternative. Three-dimensional modeling and photogrammetry protocols have been proven to be valuable resources for conservators to do a digital 3D asset that can be stored in a database or repository. Those methods provide a detailed view and more accurate morphological preservation with less invasive procedures for the samples. They also offer a long-term solution to conserve these materials with educational manipulation purposes by 3D printing the digital assets in more durable and resistant polymers (Barreau et al., 2022).

Photogrammetric processing underlies numerous computer vision technologies such as surface scanners, laser scanners, or smart cameras for data acquisition through the application of image processing algorithms. The complementation of hardware and software capabilities solution has led to automatized data acquisition processes adjusting phenomena such as refraction and reflection that create changes in dispersion and angles that lead to a chromatic image triangulating with different angles (Waltenberger et. al., 2021).

In addition, photogrammetry allows the user to perform measurements achieving high resolutions by creating points that are defined in an equation to refer to a focal length, aperture, object-in-focus distance, depth of field, and calibration in a controlled environment. The image acquisition process is a light beam triangulation method with a matrix image sensor that generates a plane of light that forms a scanning process with software for data processing on a mesh (Luhmann et al., 2013).

Considering the above statements about the utility of photogrammetry-based methods, 3D scanning with visible light provides an alternative to preserve that sample with high scientific and conservation value.

This report documents the digitization process of natural heritage skulls from a zoology university museum and a wildlife rescue center facility to test and establish the required protocols for image acquisition and processing for preservation, training, and outreach purposes harnessing the hardware and software utilities available in a digital fabrication lab. The whole methods and results described expose the lessons learned until now to offer this as a service of interest for organizations managing natural heritage.

Methodology

Some of the animal bones used for the essays described below were preserved, and the others were prepared to be scanned to utilize them for outreach and environmental education activities. Samples scanned are composed of selected parts from a collection of skulls, considering specific shapes that could be a challenge for the 3D scanner.

The following describes the workflow to go from a sample to a digitized 3D model useful for training and outreach scenarios through virtual reality or 3D printed models.

Some of the samples used for this project came from a rescue center where they applied the following process to clean and bleach the bones:

Osteological preservation

Use of safety equipment such as goggles, gloves, and masks to avoid exposition to dangerous bacteria and other chemicals throughout the entire process is mandatory. During the whole workflow, it is required to wear safety equipment to avoid the exposition to dangerous germs and chemicals.

After performing a necropsy to determine the cause of the death, the animal's skull is removed from the body, and then muscular tissue and accessory organs are separated as much as

possible from the carcass, first, the skull is buried inside a bag in which holes have been made, in a place away from animals that could dig the sample out.

The amount of time the sample is buried depends on the kind of animal and its size, for example, if it's a big bird (above 1kg), the sample will be procured from the soil after 3 weeks, in case of a small bird, it can be processed after 2 weeks. For adult mammal skulls (depending on the species) the sample is kept buried for an average time of around a month.

The sample is macerated in hot water with soap, the object is then kept under this dissolution for at least two weeks to guarantee complete saponification of greases, acceleration of protein degradation, and increase the speed of the rotting process, allowing the easy removal of any organic trace.

During the last step of this process, the bones will be bleached, and the removal of any remnant tissue or organic trace in the sample will occur. To achieve this, skull is placed inside a solution of water and Sodium Hypochlorite on a 1 to 10 ratio, the 3% available solutions for home cleaning are good enough for this purpose.

The time that the sample is kept under this solution depends on the fragility of the specimen, Its recommended to check the skull every ten minutes to avoid degradation or evidence of porosity in bones, Once there is no organic matter and the bone is completely bleached, the skull is removed from the solution and washed with enough water to remove the sodium hypochlorite and stop the chemical reactions induced by the previous steps.

To complete bleaching the piece is immersed in a solution of Hydrogen peroxide on a 1 to 10 ratio with water. In this case, the time in which the object will remain inside the solution depends on the thickness of the bones, Finally, they are washed with water to stop the degradation caused by this solution and samples are dried for 24 hours by leaving them in the sun.

Acquisition and postprocessing of 3D mesh

After selection or receiving of a sample in the digital fabrication lab, the process comprises two main steps and others that could be considered optional depending on the final product's purpose. This process occurs as follows:

The sample is scanned in a darkroom (This step requires previous calibrating and adjusting of hardware acquisition parameters depending on the 3D scanning tech to be implemented, for this case, the equipment Go!SCAN SPARK™ (Creaform, Canada) is a portable 3D scanner with 0.050 mm accuracy and 99-line white light used to target acquisition. A description of the set-up of the equipment for image acquisition is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. *Image acquisition workflow with photogrammetry-based methods, source: own study*

For organic geometry such as the organic specimens being worked with in this case, the samples are scanned from different orientations, generating two or more separated meshes merged by matching geometrical features. For mesh acquiring and optimization, two computational tools from the VXelements (Creaform, Canada) software package were used.

After partial meshes merge, little isolated artifacts can be generated, because this would cause light noise, those are removed with basic editing tools. This gross merged mesh is transferred through different packages for the postprocessing of the 3D model, according to the purpose of the essay, there are several options to prepare and optimize the new digital asset, so the mesh can be optimized for digital fabrication by 3D printing or CNC milling of molds for casting, inspected by 3D metrology or adapted and exported for virtual or augmented reality visualization in online platforms.

In both cases, visualizing or digital fabrication purposes, modeling tools allow for filling holes by creating hollow structures or modifying textures. This process also allows for the generation of new parts in the model based on the symmetry of the object. This service is related to the restoration of a piece, or even to design new parts from the scanned specimen. Inspection tools allow measurements of the similarity between meshes and geometry entities, assign planes, and export that data to be modified in CAD software.

Manufacturing processes and Quality Assurance

If the purpose of the digitization is to fabricate a physical part, 3D printing tech has become a solution capable of replicating organic features such as the ones treated in this work, after mesh optimization the file is opened in a segmentation commercial software.

FDM, Stereolithography and material jetting machines have been solutions tested for this purpose in the lab with specimens of high natural value.

To collect proof about which of these technologies are the most adequate solution for this duty, the same files were printed on three different machines. Figure 5 shows the results from a jaw scanned and printed on SLA, POLYJET and FDM.

From a qualitative point of view, all the techniques tested demonstrate promising results for the replication of specimens. In all of them there are materials-related conditions that could affect fabrication processes, for example in FDM there could be conditions like the amount of humidity in filaments, print core dimensions or even wall thickness of the model which could affect high fidelity replications, for SLA and material jetting solutions, problems such as resins compatibility or supports removal could either affect the results.

The 3D metrology capabilities available in some 3D scanners such as the one used for this report allow for the ability to measure a piece and have a quantitative notion of how much the printed parts replicate the scanned sample.

Considering that accuracy is a very significant factor in scientific and training scenarios as the interests of the rescue center involved in this essay where veterinarian wildlife medicine interns would harness replica models, a quantitative way to measure the fidelity of the replicas become very important, a quality assurance test based on 3D metrology was implemented to have a comparison between printed results and the original scan.

Visualization and Virtual reality tools

As 3D scanning technologies bring the chance to export files in several formats compatible with almost every 3-D visualization and manipulation software there are different solutions to be

used for those purposes, depending on the final users and scenarios is useful to optimize file sizes to avoid spending a long time just loading the model.

The resultant models of this work are compatible with Microsoft apps such as 3D Paint or One Drive cloud visualization tools, furthermore, were tested platforms that provide virtual reality visualizing options, in this case Sketchfab which will be used for developing didactic tools for environmental education workshops at the rescue center.

Analysis and results

Results from the acquisition and mesh processing have been exported in several compatible format files with the interest purposes of this work. The digitized models include real scale dimensions of the piece and even textures which can be saved in the 3D file or apart as a bitmap.

Samples between less than 10 centimeters (about 3.94 in) and at least 60 cm (about 1.97 ft) in length have been successfully scanned, some of them have represented a challenge for automatic setup of the scanning system such as complex structures inside craniums, very thin bones, or teeth that don't stay.

Despite that, the software platform used in this work contains the tools to repair missing structures of the cranium, such as teeth, using symmetry parts to create new mirrored in absent parts. It can also import multiple meshes from another work session to assemble them.

Figure 2 shows a crocodile cranium with significant deterioration despite careful manipulation in the museum and the results of the digitization process, This was chosen as a sample of interest for the essay because of its size (approximately 53cm (about 1.74 ft) length), both the cranium and mandible were scanned and optimized apart and then aligned and fused to generate a unique mesh that allows for a more complete visualization of the whole cranium.

Figure 2. Crocodile cranium from the Zoology Museum, source: own study.

According to (Cunningham, 2021) this type of digital asset can be useful in virtual learning scenarios because it can be manipulated with programs that allow detailed observation of the structures in distinct positions, although an underlying problem is the weight of the mesh data.

Another advantage identified in the results was the clear identification of very complex morphological structures and anatomical details from this specimen such as cranial nerves which can be noted in the 3D model image in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Crocodile skull mesh with cranial nerves detected and the ensemble of crocodile head, source: own study.

This advance is notable for academia because it provides the chance to feed databases for cranial geometric and morphometric analysis to further understand cryptic species facing diverse levels of anthropogenic threats since this kind of digitalization offers an opportunity to measure these processes (Carr et al., 2021).

Texturing and color could be features of particular interest for training and educational scenarios, Figure 4 shows a model of a dolphin cranium that includes texture data, here can be note a whitish fungus in the upper side of the cranium which could be removed in the file if were required to have a model for outreach or scientific demonstration purposes.

Figure 4. Dolphin cranium mesh with texture, source: own study.

Even when the manufacturing of high-fidelity replicas implies to consider more complex features as bone density not achievable by these techniques, according to (Edelmers et al., 2022) texture provides significant data from anatomical structures and complexity which could be useful dependent of final users.

In case the models must be printed to provide teaching resources, some of the digitized samples have been printed in three different 3D printing technologies, Figure 5 shows the case of a jaguarundi jaw (*Herpailurus yagouaroundi*) printed using FDM, SLA and Material jetting.

Jaguarundi jaw in SLA

Jaguarundi jaw in PolyJet

Jaguarundi jaw in FDM

Figure 5. Jaguarundi jaws printed with three different 3D printing technologies, source: own study.

By 3D metrology and quality assurance protocols was developed a comparison between printed models and the original scan to have a quantitative reference of the samples replication, Figure 6 and 7 shows the results of the assay for the same jaw model printed on three different materials, the analysis provides a color map where the green surfaces means a high fidelity or optimal standard deviation and deviations to hotter or cooler colors mean low fidelity those zones can be interpreted as parts or triangles included in the restoration of the model or missed features during the manufacturing process.

Figure 6. *Quality assurance results for the same jaw model printed in PolyJet and SLA technologies using commercial resins, source: own study*

Figure 7. *Quality assurance results for the same jaw model printed in the FDM technology in ABS material, source: own study*

As can be noted in color maps of Figure 6, SLA and PolyJet results provided the more accurate results for this case. On other essay, a Sloth cranium scan was compared to a 3D printed model in an Objet 30 Prime (Stratasys USA) machine. The results are in Figure 8 where can be appreciated a color map of the Standard deviation set up for the test.

Figure 8. *Color map from Quality assurance results of a sloth's cranium printed in Polyjet technology, source: own study*

For this case, the results indicate only two points with high standard deviation (1.985 mm) at the tip of the fangs and one point with lower standard deviation (-1,964 mm) at the base of the skull, those geometric differences correspond to specific zones reconstructed by software tools.

Independent of these two zones, the number of errors obtained can be attributed to systemic or aleatory mistakes that goes from the experience of the operator of the scanner, the limitation of the optical system to achieve access to distant hollow parts or even the mesh alignment implemented with software tools (Garashchenko, Kogan & Rucki, 2022).

The fact that the printed models are such an accurate replica of the bone craniums is of particular interest to stakeholders involved in this work, for example, the rescue center that provided some of the skulls, could use some of the 3D-printed models to train wildlife medicine interns.

Those 3D-printed bio models provide anatomical models that allow teachers to develop practical workshops and create educational experiences based on visual assistance strategies. (Altwal et al., 2021; da Silveira et al., 2021; Ye et al., 2023).

For visualization purposes, some of the finished meshes were uploaded to the 3D viewer platform Sketchfab. This solution was selected because it provides the setup to visualize the models on a low-cost VR lens that works integrated with mobile phones. To achieve the uploading process file sizes were optimized according to platform requirements. Figure 9, shows the results of a tiny and fragile cranium of a bird (approximately 86.690mm (about 3.41 in) length) with very thin features now preserved for digital manipulation, the platform allows both visualizations in a laptop or desktop computer or in a cell phone to change to a stereoscopic view compatible with VR lens, also, includes sharing options where an HTML code can be used for embedding it on a virtual learning environment.

Figure 9. 3D model of a grey-necked wood rail (*Aramides cajaneus*) cranium integrated into Sketchfab 3D viewer for VR visualization, source: own studio <https://skfb.ly/oKKN9>

Conclusions

The digitization processes based on photogrammetry and 3D scanning technologies provide a feasible solution for heritage-keeping particularly for scientific and knowledge preservation of high-value samples composed of biological materials exposed to degradation by environmental conditions.

Optical-based 3D printing solutions such as SLA and material jetting have been shown to give more accurate results for anatomical feature replication, which is of interest for hands-on training scenarios of vet medicine.

The digital assets resulting from those digitization processes can be harnessed for environmental education learning experiences that incorporate innovative trends and educational

tools such as virtual reality manipulation and exploration of specimens by students without the risk of losing high-value samples.

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